

Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V) as Complex with PBHA in the Nonionic Micellar Media

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One of the main uses of surfactants in analytical chemistry is in the determination of metal ions as their complexes by spectrophotometry and fluorimetry¹. In the field of metal ion complexation, at concentrations above the CMC, micelles form a ternary complex with advantageous properties, that can modify sensitivity and selectivity of the method by affecting the interferences and matrix effects². Vanadium is one of the major pollutants of the environment. Several spectrophotometric methods for determination of vanadium have been reported³. Here we describe a procedure to determine V^V with *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) in the presence of micelles of non-ionic Triton X-100. Some steel and environmental samples have been analysed for determining the vanadium content.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary work on the effect of addition of cationic surfactants (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, CTAB; cetylpyridinium chloride, CPC), anionic surfactants (sodium dodecyl sulphate and lithium dodecyl sulphate) and non-ionic surfactants (Triton X-100 (TX-100); Brij-35) to the vanadium-PBHA complex showed a considerable increase in the absorbance when surfactant solution is added. The purpose of the addition of surfactants is to enhance the colour reaction of the metal towards hydroxamic acid with increased selectivity and stability. The absorption spectra, plotted for the complex formed in chloroform among V^V, TX-100 and *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid against the reagent blank, exhibited maximum absorbance around 520 nm. Since the reagent blank had some absorbance at this region, it was used as a reference for all further measurements. No change in the position of $\lambda_{\max}$ of the complex was observed when the metal concentration was varied. When the concentration of HCl was varied between 2 and 8 M, absorption band of the chloroform extract remained intact ($\lambda_{\max} = 520$ nm) but the absorbance value was affected. For maximum colour development, the HCl concentration of the aqueous phase was found in the range 3.0–4.5 M. Among the various surfactants used for intensifying the colour reaction of V^V-PBHA complex, only the non-ionic surfactant TX-100 was found to increase the colour of complex by 2-fold. The maximum and full colour development of the ultimate species was obtained when TX-100 concentration was 0.0375–0.125 M; in practice,

0.05 M TX-100 was used. The CMC values of the surfactants were determined from surface tension measurement. At least $4-7 \times 10^{-3}$ M PBHA was found necessary for the complete extraction and maximum colour development of the complex and no adverse effect was seen in net absorbance value upto 1.6×10^{-2} M; in practice, 7.0×10^{-3} M PBHA was used. The absorbance of the extract was insensitive to the temperature alteration from 10 to 30°. The effect of presence of various electrolytes on the extraction of metal was also examined. The extraction of the analyte was unaffected with 1 M KCl/KH₄Cl/K₂SO₄ electrolytes solution, and neither a shift in $\lambda_{\max}$ nor any change in absorbance of the complex was observed. No adverse effect was observed when the volume ratio of the organic to aqueous phase was varied from 2 : 1 to 1 : 5. Hence, in all extraction work an equal volume (10 ml) of each phases was maintained. A shaking period of 2 min was sufficient for complete colour development. No change in absorbance of the extract was observed upto an extraction time of 10 min. The colour of the extracted complex remained unchanged for atleast 2 h at room temperature ($28 \pm 2^\circ$). The sequence, in which the reagents were added, was not critical. The coloured, V^V-TX-100-PBHA complex in chloroform followed the Beer's law upto 80 μg of the metal in a 10 ml ultimate solution at $\lambda_{\max}$ 520 nm, with a correlation coefficient value of 0.997. This method is applicable for detection of V^V down to a concentration level of 0.1 μg V^V per ml aqueous solution. In order to have the knowledge of precision of the method, ten independent determinations each containing 50 μg of V^V/10 ml organic phase were taken. The mean absorbance value 0.430 and a standard deviation value ± 0.005 obtained gave a relative standard deviation of ± 1.1 %. The confidence limit of the system at 95% probability was found to be $4400 \pm 30 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The effect of various diverse ions, which generally associate with the analyte, on the extraction of 50 μg V^V was studied. Almost all anions and cations examined did not interfere. The only interference caused by Fe^{III} was minimised by the addition of trisodium phosphate prior to the extraction of V^V. The tolerable amount (in mg) of various diverse ions causing error in absorbance of less than $\pm 2\%$ is as follows : Mn^{VII} (50); Pb^{II} (35); Cu^{II} (20); Ni^{II}

TABLE I—RECOVERY OF V^V FROM SAMPLES
 Vanadium (ppm)

Sl no	Sample, source and amount	Vanadium (ppm)			V determined by lit method* ppm	RSD of present method ±, %
		Added	Recovered	Actual		
1	<i>Steel</i> Obtained from Bhilai Steel Plant, Bhilai (1 g)	10	11.9	1.9	1.7	1.2
2	<i>Waste water</i> (i) Total Waste Water (TWW), obtained from Wagon Repair Shop, Raipur (200 ml)	7	12.6	5.6	5.4	1.1
	(ii) TWW, obtained from Bhilai Wires, Bhilai (200 ml)	4	15.3	11.3	14.9	1.1

*Ref 4

(18), Cr^{III} (12); Fe^{III*}, Al^{III}, Cd^{II}, sulphate, nitrate, phosphate (10 each, *masked with 2 mg trisodium phosphate); tartrate (8.0), Co^{II} (7.0); Mo^{VI}, Ba^{II}, Bi^{III} (5.0 mg each)

The method was used to determine vanadium in steel and environmental samples and the results are shown in Table 1. The results obtained are in close agreement with the established method.

Experimental

A Systronics 108 spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used. A stock solution of ammonium metavanadate (A.R., B.D.H.) was prepared in glass-distilled water. A 10 M HCl (AnalaR) was used for acidity adjustment. The chloroform (AnalaR) used was shaken with equal volume of water, distilled and stored. *N*-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) was prepared as described in the literature³ and its 0.15% (w/v) or 7.1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ solution in chloroform was used.

Procedure To an aliquot of standard solution containing V^V upto 80 µg and TX-100 (2 ml), was added HCl (3–4 ml) in total 10 ml of final aqueous solution, maintaining the temperature at $28 \pm 2^\circ$. The aqueous solution was then equilibrated with chloroform solution (5 ml) of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid for 2 min. The aqueous phase was then washed with CHCl₃ (2 × 2 ml), the combined extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g) and

made up to 10 ml with CHCl₃. A reagent blank was prepared in a similar manner. The absorbance of the extract was measured against the reagent blank.

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